

ISic0800

Honorific for [---] Lapiron Sal., son of Apollodoros

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

exedra

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Autopsy

2011-06-15

Last Change

2019-07-25 - Jonathan Prag made further revisions and improved imagery

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

First uncovered in excavation by Carettoni in 1956 (Carettoni 1961: 287 fig.22, 292 fig.27) on the steps of the west portico of the agora, between the colonnade and the rear wall of the large base in opus reticulatum. The inscription was recognised by Scibona, and the stone recovered in excavation

on 15 September 1970

Coordinates

37.997973, 14.262669

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20220

Physical Description

A slab of limestone, intact on all sides, with a lightly concave front face, and becomes thinner towards the left side. The front face and edges are more finely worked than the rest, which is merely prepared for insertion within the original monument of which it was a part. The holes for three metal staples are visible on the upper surface, and it is possible that a fourth has been lost from the top left rear.

Dimensions

Height 68 cm

Width 60 cm

Depth 13-20 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The text is regularly cut and well spaced; the terminations to the main strokes are pronounced, but not yet developed into full serifs. There is no space between words. Epsilon has a short middle bar; theta has an unattached middle bar; omicron is full size; alpha consistently has a broken bar; omega is closed and ellipsoid.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-6: 30 mm

Interlineation

interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. θεοῖς π[ᾶ]σι
2. [ὁ δᾶμ]ος τῶν Ἀλαισίνων
3. [Ἰ]Απολλοδώρου Σαλ
4. Λαπίρωνα
5. [εὐνοίας]καὶ εὐεργεσίας ἔνεκ(εν)
6. τᾶς εἰς αὐτόν

Apparatus

Earlier editions record the alpha, but it is completely lost in a crack on the upper part of the face

Translation (en)

The people of the Halaesini (dedicate) to all the gods (a statue of) [-?-] Lapiron Sal., son of Apollodoros, on account of the good will and beneficence which he has shown towards them.

Translation (it)

Il popolo degli Alesini (dedica) agli dei tutti (una statua di) [-?-] Lapiro Sal., figlio di

Apollodoros, per il benvolere e la beneficenza che ha dimostrato nei suoi confronti.

Commentary

The stone is intact on both left and right sides, making it certain that the first part of lines 2, 3, and 5 was engraved on a second stone (and so the text would have appeared symmetrical to the viewer). Burgio (2012) has demonstrated convincingly that this stone comes from the right side of an exedra monument on the steps of the west portico (exedra A), and that two additional stones stood to the left (meaning that there was space to the left not only for the beginning of this text but also for a second similar inscription in honour of another individual). The name at the start of line 3 is lost, but must have been relatively short (symmetry suggests not more than c.6 letters). Scibona suggested Dion, known from Cicero (*In Verrem* 2.2.19-24) and from brick stamps found at Halaesa. Cicero records one Apollodorus Lapiron, but the Dio of Halaesa to whom he refers in the same passage is only a relative (*propinquus*), not his son (see Facella 2006: 229-241). The abbreviation Sal at the end of line three is probably a demotic (i.e. an indicator of the part of Halaesa to which this individual belonged): the abbreviation is also attested in the bronze for Nemenios (SEG 59.1100 line 9) and elsewhere in Sicily (e.g. at Akrai, ISic1032 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1032>]; see in general Cordano, F. 1999. *Le istituzioni delle città greche di Sicilia nelle fonti epigrafiche*. In M. I. Gulletta (ed.), *Sicilia epigraphica*. Atti del convegno

internazionale Erice 15-18 Ottobre 1998 (2 vols.). Pisa: I, 149-158, at 152-4). Either εὐνοίας ('good will') or ἀρετᾶς ('virtue', 'excellence') is possible at the start of line 5, but the former is more common at Halaesa, and the pairing εὐνοίας καὶ εὐεργεσίας is already attested in ISic3351 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3351>]

The text cannot be dated precisely (second or first century BC on the basis of the letter forms), but the exedra monument itself is considered to post-date the second-century BC construction of the portico, and to belong in either the late second or early first century BC (Burgio 2012: 155), and the inscription is presumably contemporary with the construction of the exedra.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644902

PHI 331491

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-09-09): ISic0800. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4021527>

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